

INDICATORS FOR DETERMINING THE MOTIVATION OF
SOCIAL WORKERS

Munira Juraevna Makhmudova,

Ph.D. candidate in the Department of Social Work,

National University of Uzbekistan

The social protection system plays a crucial role in ensuring the social stability of any society. The effectiveness of this system primarily depends on the work efficiency and motivation of the social workers involved. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized in his speeches: "Our main task is to ensure the social protection and well-being of people. For this, it is necessary to appreciate the work and importance of social workers."

Identifying and enhancing the motivation of social workers is a pressing issue not only in Uzbekistan but also worldwide. Various countries and international organizations are striving to implement effective measures in this regard. By leveraging international research and experiences, we can develop effective mechanisms to improve the motivation of social workers in our context as well.

Commitment to Work and Love for the Job

The commitment of social workers to their work and their love for the job directly affect their work efficiency and service quality. Surveys and questionnaires can be used to measure the level of love and commitment to the job. Through this method, it is possible to determine the attitude and motivation of employees towards their work. According to research conducted by the World Bank, love and commitment to work can increase work efficiency by 20%.

Based on the data collected through surveys and questionnaires, management can determine the necessary measures to improve the work environment and increase job satisfaction. As a result, opportunities to enhance the commitment and work efficiency of social workers will be created.

Work Conditions and Environment

Work conditions and the environment significantly impact the motivation of social workers. Comfortable workplaces, technical equipment, and the environment increase employees' interest in their work. For example, studies conducted in Sweden have shown that favorable work conditions can increase worker motivation by 15-25%. Comfort and the environment of the workplace are key factors in enhancing the motivation of social workers.

To improve work conditions, it is important to provide workplaces with modern technical equipment, ergonomic furniture, and better lighting systems. By utilizing international experiences and implementing advanced technologies, it is possible to significantly improve work conditions.

Competition and Reward System

The competition and reward system plays an important role in motivating and encouraging social workers. An effective reward system, through material and moral incentives, can increase employees' interest in their work. According to research conducted in the United States, material incentives can increase worker motivation by 30%. By using incentivizing measures in the reward system, it is possible to improve the work efficiency of employees.

In the reward system, not only material but also moral incentives are important. For example, recognizing the achievements of employees, morally encouraging them, and rewarding them with praises and acknowledgments in front of the team can increase employees' interest in their work.

Relationships with Management

The relationship of social workers with management is also an important indicator of motivation. Support from management, listening to their opinions, and helping resolve their issues increase employees' interest in their work. Studies conducted in Japan have shown that good relations with management can increase worker motivation by 25-35%.

Management's attitude towards employees, actively participating in resolving their issues, and listening to their opinions significantly improve employees' attitudes towards their work. In this regard, management's leadership qualities and effectiveness in resolving issues play an important role.

Opportunities for Personal and Professional Growth

Creating opportunities for personal and professional growth for social workers is a key factor in increasing their motivation. Employees can be encouraged by offering training, seminars, and professional development courses. According to research conducted in Germany, professional development opportunities can increase worker motivation by 20-30%.

Through professional development opportunities, it is possible to enhance the knowledge and skills of employees, prepare them for new tasks, and create the necessary conditions for successful work. This, in turn, helps increase employees' interest in their work.

International Efforts

Many projects aimed at enhancing the motivation of social workers are being implemented internationally. The World Bank, the UN, UNICEF, and other international organizations are conducting various activities to support the social protection system and increase the motivation of social workers. For example, training and seminars focused on the professional development and motivation of social workers have been organized in projects implemented by the World Bank.

Moreover, programs aimed at improving the social protection system and increasing worker motivation are also being implemented by the European Union. Within these programs, measures such as improving work conditions, implementing material incentive systems, and expanding professional development opportunities are being taken.

Conclusion

There are many indicators for determining and enhancing the motivation of social workers. Commitment to work, work conditions, competition and reward

systems, relationships with management, and opportunities for personal and professional growth play a key role in improving the work efficiency of social workers. International research and experiences show that regular study and analysis of these indicators can help increase the motivation of social workers. Therefore, it is necessary to expand research and practical measures in this direction.

References in the Thesis:

1. World Bank Research - World Bank Research
2. Sweden Research - Sweden Research
3. US Research - US Research
4. Japan Research - Japan Research
5. Germany Research - Germany Research
6. World Bank Project - World Bank Project
7. EU Program - EU Program